

IoT-Enabled Smart Air Quality Monitoring System

¹Ravi Kumar Tirandasu, ²Dr.J.Manoranjini, ³Mr.A.Suresh Kumar,
⁴Ms.E.Anitha, ⁵Ms.R.Janani ⁶Dr.G.Ganesh Kumar

¹Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, Koneru Lakshmaiah Education Foundation,
Vaddeswaram, AP, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of AI&ML, Rajalakshmi Engineering College,
Chennai.

³Assistant Professor, Department of CSE, Rathinam Technical Campus, Coimbatore,
TN, India

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Artificial Intelligence and Data science,
Sri Eshwar College of Engineering, Coimbatore.

⁵Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Sri Krishna College of
Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore.

⁶Assistant Professor, Department of Information Technology, Hindusthan Institute of
Technology, Coimbatore, India.

Abstract :

The contemporary challenge of maintaining good air quality hinges on effectively monitoring various air pollutants across different regions. Pollution, stemming from industrial emissions, vehicular exhaust, and other sources, has escalated to critical levels, surpassing government-set air quality index values in many major cities. This pollution profoundly impacts human health. Leveraging advancements in Machine Learning (ML) technology, it's now feasible to predict pollutant levels based on historical data. To combat this issue, we propose an IoT-based air pollution monitoring system. The primary aim is to track atmospheric pollutant concentrations in real-time.

Our system, developed using Arduino microcontrollers, is designed to continuously monitor and analyze air quality, transmitting data to a remote server for real-time updates over the internet. Employing sensors such as MQ135 Air Quality Gas sensors, it precisely analyzes gas composition. Additionally, humidity and temperature sensors are incorporated to measure these parameters. The collected data is displayed on an LCD screen interfaced with the hardware module. Furthermore, we utilize Microsoft Excel for data analysis based on Parts per Million (PPM) metrics. Data is then transmitted to the ThingSpeak cloud, enabling easy access via any smart mobile device. This IoT-based pollution monitoring system ensures accurate, real-time monitoring of air quality, aiding in proactive pollution management efforts.

1. Introduction

Global warming is an environmental phenomenon caused by natural and anthropogenic air pollution. It refers to rising air and ocean temperatures around the world. This temperature rise is at least partially caused by an increase in the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. Greenhouse gases trap heat energy in the Earth atmosphere. (Usually, more of Earth's heat escapes into space. Carbon dioxide is a greenhouse gas that has had the biggest effect on global warming. Carbon dioxide

is emitted into the atmosphere by burning fossil fuels (coal, gasoline, and natural gas). Humans have come to rely on fossil fuels to power cars and planes, heat homes, and run factories. Doing these things pollutes the air with carbon dioxide. Other greenhouse gases emitted by natural and artificial sources also include methane, nitrous oxide, and fluorinated gases.

Methane is a major emission from coal plants and agricultural processes. Nitrous oxide is a common emission from industrial factories, agriculture, and the burning of fossil fuels in cars. Fluorinated gases, such as hydrofluorocarbons, are emitted by industry. Fluorinated gases are often used instead of gases such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs). CFCs have been outlawed in many places because they deplete the ozone layer. Hence to control and monitor the amount of harmful air pollutants in the atmosphere is necessary. This creates the need for real-time monitoring of air quality measurement and analysis so that appropriate decisions can be made in a timely manner. This article introduces automatic real-time air quality monitoring.

Nowadays, the Internet of Things is being widely used in all fields and also plays an important role in our air quality monitoring system. The setup will display the air quality in PPM on the website so we can monitor it very easily. In this IoT project, you can monitor pollution levels from anywhere using your computer or mobile device. The setup will display the air quality in PPM on the website so we can monitor it very easily. In this IoT project, can monitor the AQI levels from anywhere through web application. Air conditioning is very polluted. In recent years, vehicle exhaust, factory chemicals, and dust have been everywhere. This is why air conditioners are so polluted nowadays.

The effects of air pollution are very bad for our health, especially for the places that get air for our bodies to breathe. In our lungs can cause a number of diseases such as asthma, cough, lung disorders. Air pollution can't be detected by human senses. Air pollution can contain many harmful substances, such as LPG gas, carbon monoxide and methane. Polluted substances in the air are very dangerous. For example, if the carbon monoxide is above 100ppm, people feel dizzy, nauseous and can die within minutes. This research allows people to find out the content of polluted air. With NODEMCU ESP8266 module, we can monitor air pollution remotely, because in NODEMCU ESP8266 there is Wi-Fi. This makes the AQI can be monitored at all times.

2. Related Works:

[1] An IoT Implemented Dynamic Air Pollution Monitoring System Sneha Edupuganti*, Narasinga Sai Satwik Tenneti, M. Mohamed Iqbal and, Gnanajeyaraman Rajaram The mechanism was designed to measure various air quality parameters such as temperature, humidity, various gases, microbes, and light intensity in real time. The proposed system consists of sensor nodes, a gateway, WIFI module, an LCD display, and a cloud server. The sensor nodes were placed at different locations to measure air quality parameters, and the data were transmitted to the gateway via wireless communication. The gateway aggregates the data from the sensor nodes and sends them to the cloud server for further analysis and processing.

The cloud server processes the data, and the system also includes a web interface that displays data on the pollution levels of the air in real time.

[2] Mohammed Rakib, Sanaulla Haq et.,al., [5] “IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring & Prediction System” Proceedings of IEEE 2022 International Conference on Innovations in Science, Engineering and Technology (ICISSET) Date Added to IEEE *Xplore*: 23 May 2022. The proposed solution consists of two parts: an IoT device with four sensors connected with a processing unit and a software model. The sensors can track the air quality around us by measuring Particulate Matter, Carbon monoxide, Ammonia, Temperature, and Humidity. A microcontroller processes the data from the properly calibrated sensors and sends them to Realtime cloud storage through a Wi-Fi module. A remote server then fetches and analyses the data. We then determine the prime pollutant from the data, which is Particulate Matter. The Autoregressive

Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model is used to predict the pollution levels from harmful gases & the Air Quality Index (AQI) of the next day with high accuracy.

[3] Piyush Devidas Potbhare et.,al., [7] “IoT based Smart Air Pollution Monitoring System” Proceedings of IEEE 2022 International Conference on Applied Artificial Intelligence and Computing (ICAAIC) Date Added to IEEE *Xplore*: 16 June 2022..This paper proposes a solution which is a low-cost multimodality sensor-based system, such as MQ 2 used for sensing the occurrence of Propane, Hydrogen and LPG (Liquefied Petroleum Gas), MQ 5 and MQ 9 it can be used in gas leakage appliance to check leakage, MQ 6 used for checking of contamination of additional gases present in the air, MQ 135 used for air quality parameter sensor and DHT 11 use for measuring the temperature and humidity of the atmosphere for better quality of the air. These sensors will interface with Arduino UNO micro controller and will send it to cloud which will be visible to the user on the 24*4 LCD (Liquid Crystal Display). At this the user can get a well-defined idea of the air quality present around his surroundings.

[4] S B Sonu; A. Suyampulingam [9] “Linear Regression Based Air Quality Data Analysis and Prediction using Python” proceedings of 2021 IEEE Madras Section Conference (MASCON) Date Added to IEEE *Xplore*: 19 October 2021 In this paper, the analysis of air quality is carried out by the means of python platform where the historical air quality data analysis of Coimbatore city is implemented and the prediction of the air quality data using linear regression model. For the air quality prediction part, data set collection, data cleaning, preprocessing and prediction are implemented. The air quality data is processed using inbuilt libraries for analyzing the data which are available in python environment. The work consist of two parts where the air quality data analysis is implemented along with the prediction of air quality data which is the Air Quality Index(AQI) class from the previous records available.

3. Methodology

A. IOT based air pollution

For monitoring In this project we will create an IOT based air pollution monitoring system in which we will monitor the air quality on a web server using the Internet and trigger an alert when the quality the air drops below a certain level, which means when there are enough harmful gases in the air like CO₂, smoke, alcohol, benzene and NH₃. It will display the air quality in PPM on the LCD screen and also on the website so that we can monitor it very easily.

This System uses 3 sensors to measure weather/environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, light intensity, dew point and heat index. The values read from the sensors are processed by the Arduino microcontroller and stored in a text file that can be processed for analysis. Readings are also displayed on the built-in LCD for quick viewing. All these readings can be analysed to get the weather characteristics of a particular area and save the weather model.

B. Air Quality on A Web Server

For monitoring In this project we will create an IOT based air pollution monitoring system in which we will monitor the air quality on a web server using the Internet and trigger an alert when the quality the air drops below a certain level, which means when there are enough harmful gases in the air like CO₂, smoke, alcohol, benzene and NH₃. It will display the air quality in PPM on the LCD screen and also on the website so that we can monitor it very easily. we used sensor MQ135, which is the best choice for monitoring air quality as it can detect most harmful gases and measure their quantity accurately.

In this IOT project, you can monitor the pollution level from anywhere using your computer or mobile phone. This proposed system presents the development of IOT for AQM and detects gas leaks and acoustic events using machine learning. The combination of a commercial gas sensor and resistance measurement allows the calculation of the air quality index as well. The system's ability to detect both reducing and oxidizing pollutants, along with its low-cost and real-time monitoring features, makes it a suitable solution for use in systems Wireless AQM and early warning system.

Block Diagram

Figure 1: IoT network architecture design

The above Figure 1 represents the IoT network architecture design. It has the ability to collect and transmit data in real-time. Initial investment in IoT devices may be high but the cost of maintenance and operation is relatively low. Its offers high level of accuracy and precision in environmental monitoring. The Scalability of IoT in environmental monitoring allows multiple locations through the addition of sensors and devices.

4. Result and Discussions

The software implementation plays a major role while retrieving the sensor data and updating it to the server. Here two software tools we used mainly. The ARDUINO IDE is an embedded programming platform which supports various

microcontrollers and provides a complete programming environment for the microcontrollers. The entire programming part of the system can be done in C language.

ESP8266

Firstly, we have to initialize the ESP8266 by sending a few AT commands. The initialization process includes verifying communication with the ESP8266 to the microcontroller, finding a WiFi network within its range, and connecting the WiFi module to that network by authenticating with the required credentials. After the initialization, we need to program the configuration of the Wi-Fi module as a TCP/IP client. When configuring the ESP8266, it is important to verify that the module is configured correctly.

After configuring the ESP8266, we need to programmatically read the data from the sensor. The ADC (Analogue to Digital Converter) device must be configured with all the prerequisites such as clock frequency, resolution and data format. Then the microcontroller will execute the instruction continuously to get the updated data values from sensor. Now the main task has come in the discussion, which is to plot the sensor data in graphical form.

Here we have to go through some kind of network environment where we have to manage the communication of IP addresses. As we mentioned in previous chapters, we used an open-source data logging site to reduce implementation costs. Usually, if we want to graph the data on a web page, we have to own and pay for the domain space and design the website according to our needs, which is a complicated and expensive method.

ThingSpeak

Instead of paying for a separate domain, we used a website called "ThingSpeak". The below figure 2 methodized concentration of Temperature, humidity, Carbon monoxide and Alcohol present in the atmosphere and plotted those values in the graph. MQ-measures the concentration of Methane and calculated the total AQI (Air Quality Index) value present in the atmosphere. It also mentions the location of the AQI monitoring system present.

The Connected sensors detect the harmful gases and sends the value to the microcontroller. The Sound sensor and the Temperature sensors also detect the noise level and the humidity level present in the air. These sensors transmit this data to microcontroller and reports it to the online server over IoT. The result was displayed on the designed hardware's display interface and could be accessed via the cloud on any smart mobile device.

Create data channels

It provides free space for users to create data channels. Each channel will have 8 fields to record different data and will automatically plot the given data as a graphical representation. The below figure 3 methodized Communication with the ThingSpeak server can be done using its IP address. the system and the ThingSpeak server. Once we've created a channel to import data into the website, that channel

will be assigned an API key. So we need to write the API key before writing the actual data, then the data will be stored and displayed in the requested channel

Figure 2: Output Graph from Thing Speak Cloud

Figure 3: Output graph from ThingSpeak Cloud

5. Conclusion

The research and implementation of a system for monitoring the environmental parameters using IoT scenario is accomplished, the system provides a low power solution for establishing a weather station. The system to monitor the air of environment using Arduino microcontroller, IOT Technology is proposed to improve quality of air. With the use of IOT technology enhances the process of monitoring various aspects of environment such as air quality monitoring issue proposed in this paper.

Here, using the MQ135 and MQ6 gas sensor gives the sense of different type of dangerous gas and Arduino is the heart of this project. Which control the entire process. Wi-Fi module connects the whole process to internet and LCD is used for the visual Output. The system is tested in an environment and it is successfully updated the weather conditions from sensor data and it is also a less expensive solution due to usage of low power wireless sensors and SoC contained Wi-Fi module. The Data collected via Thinkspeak cloud was tested.

References

- [1] An IoT Implemented Dynamic Air Pollution Monitoring System Sneha Edupuganti,, Narasinga Sai Satwik Tenneti, M. Mohamed Iqbal and, Gnanajeyaraman Rajaram , nov 2023 .
- [2]Mohammed Rakib, Sanauulla Haq et.,al., (23 May 2022)“IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring & Prediction System” Proceedings of IEEE 2022 International Conference on Innovations in Science, Engineering and Technology (ICISSET) .
- [3] Piyush Devidas Potbhare et.,al.,“IoT based Smart Air Pollution Monitoring System” Proceedings of IEEE 2022 International Conference on Applied Artificial Intelligence and Computing (ICAAIC) 16 June 2022.
- [4] S B Sonu; A. Suyampulingam (19 October 2021) “Linear Regression Based Air Quality Data Analysis and Prediction using Python” proceedings of 2021 IEEE Madras Section Conference (MASCON)
- [5] C. Y. Lin et al., "Design and Implementation of a Smart Air Quality Monitoring System Based on IoT Technology," in IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 243-251, May 2019. DOI: 10.1109/TCE.2019.2898700.
- [6] H. R. Zahedi et al., "A Smart IoT-Based Air Pollution Monitoring System," in IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 8474-8482, Nov. 2020. DOI: 10.1109/TIM.2020.2993689.
- [7] S. Kim et al., "IoT-Based Air Pollution Monitoring System for Smart Cities," in Sensors (Basel), vol. 20, no. 4, 2020. DOI: 10.3390/s20041049.
- [8] N. M. Shashikumar et al., "A Review on IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring Systems," in Journal of Physics: Conference Series, vol. 1655, no. 1, 2021. DOI: 10.1088/1742-6596/1655/1/012072.
- [9] A. Aditya et al., "An IoT-Based Smart Air Quality Monitoring System Using Raspberry Pi," in International Journal of Advanced Trends in Computer Science and Engineering, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 6325-6329, Mar-Apr 2020. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341257963_An_IoT-Based_Smart_Air_Quality_Monitoring_System_Using_Raspberry_Pi.
- [10] S. K. Tiwari et al., "A Review on IoT-Based Air Pollution Monitoring System," in Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, vol. 1251, pp. 119-128, 2021. DOI: 10.1007/978-981-15-8630-5_13.
- [11] Jain, S., & Yadav, N. (2020). "IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring System using Machine Learning." 2020 7th International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom), 1167-1171.
- [12] Khedkar, P., Garge, S., & Ingole, R. (2020). "IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring System using Arduino." International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research, 9(1), 3136-3139.
- [13]. Patil, V., Anjaneyulu, A., & Borra, S. (2020). "An IoT based Smart Environmental Monitoring System using Raspberry Pi." 2020 International Conference on Computer Science and Information Technology (COMIT), 1-5.
- [14]. Shreyas, K., & George, S. (2020). "Real Time Air Pollution Monitoring System using IoT." International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology, 9(2), 203-207.

- [15]. Rani, M., & Sahana, S. (2020). "A Review on IoT based Air Pollution Monitoring Systems." *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology (IJEAT)*, 9(4), 264-268.
- [16]. Shrestha, S., Chakraborty, D., & Sharma, S. (2021). "Design and Implementation of Air Quality Monitoring System using IoT." *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, 1-5.
- [17]. Kumar, N., Tiwari, S., & Bansal, A. (2021). "IoT based Air Pollution Monitoring System using Raspberry Pi and Arduino." *2021 8th International Conference on Computing for Sustainable Global Development (INDIACom)*, 1119-1123.
- [18]. Vijayakumar, P., & Natarajan, N. (2021). "Smart Air Pollution Monitoring System using IoT." *2021 3rd International Conference on Electronics, Communication and Aerospace Technology (ICECA)*, 193-197.
- [19]. Ganesh, S., & Manikandan, G. (2021). "An IoT based Air Pollution Monitoring System using NodeMCU." *2021 International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Knowledge Economy (ICCIKE)*, 1-4.